

WHAT CAN WE LEARN ABOUT RESPIRATORY DISEASES FROM COVID-19?

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Abstract

Health care and other societal systems, as well as the global economy, have been profoundly affected by the COVID-19 pandemic. In most humanitarian emergencies, poorer developing nations have been hardest hit, and disadvantaged groups, especially those living in poverty and marginalized, have been disproportionately affected. During the initial phase of the pandemic, national response strategies to COVID-19 were largely similar in scope, but the timeliness, scale, and assertiveness of the responses varied greatly.

Key words: Pathogen, exotic, acute bronchitis, pneumonia, SARS, influenza, pharyngitis, sinusitis, otitis media

While COVID-19 was previously thought to be a harmless pathogen, it was found in natural habitats in exotic Asian animals as a source of unremarkable respiratory (and intestinal) diseases.

The world is changing rapidly. Viruses' genetic properties change during continuous regeneration, allowing them to better adapt to living conditions and find more suitable hosts. Additionally, people are increasingly disregarding the

hazards of microbiological contamination, thereby becoming both infected and spreading infections rapidly.

Respiratory disease history

Among the leading causes of death in the world (24–25%) for the past 15 years have been infectious diseases. In comparison with other acute pathologies, bacterial infections of the respiratory tract are the most common cause of long-term disability.

It is estimated that more than 200 million respiratory tract infections occur worldwide every year (outside of pandemic periods). In fact, only about a third of these visits are made through health workers, primarily through outpatient networks. These networks make up more than 10% of all visits to a physician.

Antibiotics are generally used for respiratory infections half the time as outpatients and one-third of the time as inpatients. A total of 15 billion dollars of direct medical costs and 9 billion dollars of indirect medical costs are incurred in the United States each year for the treatment of respiratory infections.

Respiratory diseases and their forms

Infections of the respiratory tract are most prevalent in the elderly and include SARS, influenza, pharyngitis, sinusitis, otitis media, bronchitis, and pneumonia. Upper respiratory tract infections include acute bronchitis and pneumonia. Lower respiratory tract infections are acute bronchitis and pneumonia.

It is important to note that complications, which can sometimes result in death, can escalate the problem of high morbidity and significant economic losses. Older adults who are 65 or older are most likely to die from pneumonia and influenza combined.

Affected by COVID-19

The heart, lungs, brain, kidneys, blood arteries, and other important human systems and organs may suffer major consequences as a result of COVID-19. Despite the fact that COVID-19 is a respiratory illness, medical professionals understand that it is a multi-systemic disease that can impact any organ.

Its effects are felt by all medical professionals, including trichologists, psychiatrists, and pulmonologists. Even after recovering from COVID-19, many people still voice complaints about their health. The complaints range widely, from thrombosis to hair loss.

Given the similarities of respiratory infection symptoms, it is crucial for effective therapy to quickly distinguish COVID-19 from seasonal SARS, influenza, and bacterial pathology.

The importance of this component is increased by the discovery that many COVID-19 cases did not respond well to standard antiviral medications, despite these medications' shown efficacy in treating seasonal acute respiratory viral infections and influenza.

What methods are available to get our respiratory system functioning normally again

Antiviral therapy is the first thing we do. It may not always be possible to use it for a specific patient, though. Antiviral medication is therefore of limited effect if a patient shows up 5–6 days after the infection started.

The symptoms brought on by the disease are the next challenge for doctors. Anti-inflammatory therapy, therapy to treat coagulation issues, and then therapy to treat hypoxemia or respiratory failure may all be necessary as part of the course of treatment. Each patient's unique characteristics along the course of the disease will, of course, affect how they respond to treatment, which will vary depending on the situation.

Respiratory illnesses in the future

Today, acute respiratory infections continue to have a dominant position in the structure of human morbidity, mostly because the prevalence of viral infections tends to increase seasonally. Undoubtedly, this fact contributes to significant economic losses due to the expense of medical care and temporary impairment.

The complex interaction between lung bacteria and viruses is a significant concern. The early detection of respiratory infections in order to make the best treatment decisions is a crucial responsibility of the medical field, especially for outpatient doctors.

Developing pulmonary fibrosis

The body's reaction to inflammation or injury is fibrosis. In between 10 and 15 percent of people who recover from viral pneumonia linked to COVID-19 experience it. Experts warn of a developing tuberculosis epidemic in addition to the measles outbreak. Mass population examinations (preventive and control fluorography) were nearly never done because of quarantine regulations. Many people may experience the early stages of tuberculosis at this time, which can only be identified with fluorography. In addition, COVID-19 survivors frequently have impaired immune systems and poor lung health, which makes them vulnerable to the TB infection.

As a systemic illness, COVID-19

Although COVID-19 generally manifests as respiratory symptoms, it would be incorrect to categorize it as a confined respiratory disease. The neurological system is harmed and the intestines are frequently contaminated even with a moderate type of COVID-19. At the same time, lung injury is primarily linked to the risk of the infectious process spreading and the emergence of serious systemic disease. Finally, the addition of infectious thrombotic microvasculitis (endothelins) to bronchopneumonia-alveolitis not only produces a substrate for respiratory failure but also increases the risk of viruses entering the bloodstream.

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